

Investigating atmospheric aerosol's influence on Crab measurements using HESS and VERITAS telescopes

Samanta Morales Sanchez de Lozada

Physics Department, Università degli Studi di Trieste,
Via Alfonso Valerio, 2, Trieste, Italy
samantasanchezdelozada@gmail.com

Julia Favaro

Physics Department, Università degli Studi di Pisa,
Largo Bruno Pontecorvo 3, Pisa, Italy
j.favaro@studenti.unipi.it

Supervisors: Dr. Sylvia Jiechen Zhu .

Group leaders: Dr. Emma de Ona Wilhelmi .

Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron DESY,
Platanenallee 6, Zeuthen, Germany

The project carried out during the summer school concerned the phenomenon of the Crab Nebula's flares. The objective was to gain a deeper understanding of the systematics observed in the H.E.S.S and VERITAS data to combine these datasets and enhance the sensitivity in order to detect the flares. Using GAMMAPY, we analyzed an extensive dataset: 221 hours of H.E.S.S observations and 721 hours from VERITAS.

In order to incorporate the effects of atmospheric variations into our analysis, we drew upon data from the Copernicus atmospheric survey to study flux dynamics. Preliminary results suggest that if the aerosol concentration is not taken into account in the instrument response functions (IRFs), it can reduce the accuracy of air-shower reconstructions and the sensitivity to transient VHE emissions. We hypothesize that higher aerosol optical depth values (AOD), indicating lower atmospheric transparency, diminish the observed gamma-ray flux.

Keywords: Crab Nebula; Telescopes: H.E.S.S, VERITAS; Copernicus; systematics; GAMMAPY; AOD: Aerosol Optical Depth

1 Introduction

1.1 Crab Nebula

The Crab Nebula is a supernova remnant resulting from a core-collapse supernova, forming a pulsar wind nebula powered by a rapidly rotating neutron star with a strong magnetic field at its center. One of the most well-known and studied properties of the Crab Nebula is its Spectral Energy Distribution (SED), which extends from radio frequencies up to PeV energies. The SED is composed of two distinct components: a synchrotron component up to 0.1 GeV and an inverse Compton at higher energies. The synchrotron component is generated by the acceleration of electrons and positrons within the crab nebula, following the magnetic field lines, while the inverse Compton one results from the scattering of relativistic electrons with less energetic photons, thereby increasing their energy. These photons may originate from external sources, such as the cosmic microwave background (CMB), or be generated by the synchrotron process itself. In the latter case, we will be addressing the phenomenon of Synchrotron Self-Compton (SSC).

Historically, the Crab Nebula's flux was assumed to be constant over time, reinforcing its role as a standard candle. However, this assumption was challenged by the detection of flares by space-based missions FERMI^[1] and AGILE^[2]. These flares, detected in the GeV range with the most energetic reaching 100 GeV, exhibited varying durations and energy ranges, suggesting they originated from different regions and processes. The hypothesis that these flares are caused by changes in the magnetic field remains under investigation, with the exact processes and locations of these events still unknown. The expectation of observing a TeV flare in conjunction with a GeV flare is based on the potential increase in synchrotron emission, which could result in more photons being up-scattered to the TeV range by the same electron population. Ground-based telescopes, such as the Imaging Atmospheric Cherenkov Telescopes (IACTs) HESS and VERITAS, are essential for observing these potential TeV flares. However, to date, no Cherenkov telescopes have detected such flares, possibly due to atmospheric effects.^{[3][4][5][6]} To enhance sensitivity, we can perform a dual study on the same energy range using different IACTs.

1.2 Our hypothesis

IACTs are built to measure the Cherenkov light emitted in gamma-ray-induced particle showers in the atmosphere. Our analysis is based on pre-processed data where the direction and energy of the primary gamma-ray have been reconstructed

from recorded shower images using the ImPACT algorithm (Parsons & Hinton 2014). As part of this framework, Monte Carlo simulations have been utilized to model how detectors respond to air showers under specific conditions. These simulated detector responses are then compared with observational data to estimate air shower properties.

We hypothesize that lower atmospheric transparency, indicated by higher Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) values, shifts the observed gamma-ray spectrum towards higher energies. AOD is defined as the integral of the aerosol extinction coefficient over a vertical column of air. The primary concern regarding increased AOD value is the introduction of systematic errors in the air showers' properties since these conditions are not included in the Monte Carlo simulations. Lower energy photons are more likely to be scattered or absorbed by aerosols, leaving a higher proportion of higher energy photons to be detected. This diminishes the overall flux and introduces systematic misconstruction of the air showers. The impact of this smearing on the final result can depend on a combination of multiple aspects such as the binning resolution, the true physical properties and distribution of the observed air-shower events, as well as the specific differences between the actual and simulated observing conditions.^{[7][8]}

Traditionally, quality cuts are applied by the IACT collaborations to exclude datasets that are not collected under optimal atmospheric conditions. However, this approach is not feasible in the case of transient phenomena, where measurements are confined to a narrow time frame. A potential solution to this issue is the generation of atmospheric transmission profiles under specific conditions. These profiles would be employed to estimate the expected number of Cherenkov photons to reach the IACT. Subsequently, a comparison could be made between this estimation and the results of the simulations, to obtain a correction factor. This correction factor could be applied to adjust the IRFs and shower energy estimations.

In this work, we estimate the Pearson correlation coefficient between unfiltered Crab Nebula observations from H.E.S.S. and VERITAS and the aerosol levels concurrent to those runs. By understanding and correcting these atmospheric effects, we hope to improve the accuracy and sensitivity of ground-based gamma-ray observations, thereby advancing our knowledge of transient VHE emissions and their underlying processes.

2 Methods

We performed separate analyses using the standard analysis tools of the GammaPy package (v1.2; GammaPy developers 2024).

2.1 GAMMAPY

For the high-level data analysis of gamma-ray observations, we utilized the open-source Python package GAMMAPY. This package processes data from the DL3 level (IRFs, individual observations, gamma-ray-like events) up to the DL5/6 level (spectra, light curves, correlations). Therefore having as an objective to extract the physical quantities of the sources and to produce a scientific product. GAMMAPY is extensively used in H.E.S.S. publications and data analysis and is also employed by the MAGIC, VERITAS, and HAWC collaborations. It is set to become the primary analysis tool for the Cherenkov Telescope Array (CTA).

For low-level data analysis tasks such as calibration, event reconstruction, and selection, which are specific to the instruments used, we relied on the respective pipelines provided by each collaboration group.

Using GAMMAPY, we processed the raw data to remove residual background noise and prepare it for further analysis with reflected regions background rejection standard techniques. We calculated the brightness of the Crab Nebula over time and estimated its flux by generating light curves and performing flux estimation.

2.2 Copernicus

The Copernicus program is a European Union initiative that processes information derived from both satellite and ground-based observations. Satellite data are collected from the SENTINEL satellite family, with the program commencing with the launch of Sentinel-1 in 2014. Ground-based data are gathered from stations situated on land, at sea, and in the air.

The program offers a range of services, including atmosphere, land, climate change monitoring, security, and emergency services. All data are freely available and have undergone thorough processing and analysis. In this project, we focused on atmospheric data, specifically the atmospheric component data, using the Sentinel-3 constellation, which ESA and EUMETSAT operate. This constellation comprises three different instruments that work together to monitor and understand various climatic phenomena on a global scale.

In particular, we utilized the Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) measurements at a 550 nm wavelength. The data are collected globally every three hours. Us-

ing the Pandas Python package, we interpolated the correct values for each of our runs.

2.3 Spectral analysis

Data from both collaborations were selected by placing the region of interest (ROI) within a radius of 5 degrees from the position of the Crab Nebula. This approach ensured that only data from this specific region was included in the analysis. To maintain comparability, identical region masks were applied in both cases, incorporating a catalog of nearby bright stars.

Particular care was taken in selecting the energy axis. It was crucial to ensure that the chosen energy axis was neither too close to the true energy axis nor starting at the energy value of interest. Before processing the dataset through our background rejection pipeline, we ensured that the containment corrections were accurately applied.

Finally, a spectral fit was performed to identify the optimal model for each telescope. For the HESS data, an Exponential Cut-Off Power Law was applied (eq. 1), which is the standard model for H.E.S.S. data. The reference energy E_0 was also set to 1 TeV.

$$\phi(E) = \phi_0 \cdot \left(\frac{E}{E_0}\right)^{-\Gamma} e^{-(\lambda E)^\alpha} \quad (1)$$

The resulting graph can be seen in Fig. 1, for the following best-fit parameters:

$$\Gamma = 2.44 \pm 0.01$$

$$\lambda = 0.07 \pm 0.01 \text{ TeV}^{-1}$$

$$\phi_0 = (3.34 \pm 0.03) \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}\text{TeV}^{-1} .$$

Figure 1: Spectral fit with an exponential cut-off on the complete HESS dataset. No energy threshold was implemented nor the selection of "significant" datasets.

The spectral fit for VERITAS was performed using a Log Parabola (eq. 2) with a reference energy E_0

of 1 TeV. The resulting graph can be seen in Fig.2.

$$\phi(E) = \phi_0 \cdot \left(\frac{E}{E_0}\right)^{-\alpha - \beta \log\left(\frac{E}{E_0}\right)} \quad (2)$$

The best-fit parameters obtained are indicated below and are consistent with the results obtained for H.E.S.S. In particular, the spectral index α and the amplitude ϕ_0 are compatible within respectively 1σ and 4σ with the H.E.S.S. findings.

$$\alpha = 2.449 \pm 0.002$$

$$\beta = 0.096 \pm 0.002$$

$$\phi_0 = (3.47 \pm 0.01) \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ TeV}^{-1} .$$

Figure 2: Spectral fit with a log parabola on flux points from VERITAS unfiltered datasets, avoiding any atmospheric selection usually applied in data selection.

Although we would expect the same spectrum since both observatories are observing the Crab Nebula, H.E.S.S. has a slightly higher energy threshold, making it less sensitive to lower energy flux. Consequently, the best-fit model for H.E.S.S. flux points is an Exponential Cut-off Parabola, while for VERITAS, it's a Log Parabola, when considered as separate datasets. Fig. 3(a) presents a final comparison between the two best-fit functions for flux points of these two telescopes.

The mean flux density is about $4.99 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ in the case of VERITAS's dataset, while it's approximately $2.30 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ for HESS. Notably, if we examine the flux histogram in Fig. 3(b), we see that spectra overlap when accounting for systematic uncertainties of 20%. The lower flux distribution observed with H.E.S.S. could be attributed to higher AOD values at certain observation times, and the fact that in this observations we are not using the middle telescope.

As illustrated in Fig. 4, the initial challenge encountered in our analysis, was the energy threshold of

our instruments: our datasets were biased towards higher fluxes. To conduct an accurate analysis of the data, it was necessary to divide it into two energy ranges: 0.2 to 1 TeV (section 3.1) and 1 to 10 TeV (section 3.2).

In addition for VERITAS, a more in-depth look at the AOD variation with different seasonal atmospheric models is provided respectively in section 4.2 and 4.3.

(a) Comparison between best fit functions on H.E.S.S. and VERITAS flux points, reflecting how, even if they are observing the same object, H.E.S.S. is less sensitive to lower energy.

(b) Flux distribution for the two telescopes. H.E.S.S. tends to have a lower flux, probably because of adverse AOD conditions.

Figure 3: Comparison between H.E.S.S. and VERITAS observations of the same ROI.

Figure 4: Histogram of flux values for H.E.S.S. observations in log space. No energy division, nor the value of $\sqrt{\text{TS}}$, was chosen.

3 H.E.S.S analysis

The High Energy Stereoscopic System (H.E.S.S.) is a five-telescope array situated in Namibia at an altitude of 1800 m. The instrument is capable of detecting gamma rays within the energy range of GeV up to 100 TeV. The array is composed of four smaller telescopes, each with a mirror area of 108 m², arranged in a square formation, with the largest telescope, which has a mirror area of 614 m², situated in the center. An important characteristic of the H.E.S.S. site is the burning season, which occurs between April and October. This will consequently increase the quantity of aerosol, meaning the Aerosol Optical Depth at 500 nm (AOD_{550}), increases as discussed in 1.2.

In order to conduct this study, 221 hours of Crab Nebula data were employed. The used data span 15 years, from 2004 to 2019. In Fig. 5 one can find these observations with the increase in the AOD values during the burning season.

Figure 5: H.E.S.S Crab Nebula observation dates in pink with the burning seasons highlighted in grey and AOD values in blue.

The objective of this study, as said in section 1.2, was to determine whether a correlation exists be-

tween HESS data and AOD values and to investigate the Crab flux variations in response to these. Furthermore, an attempt was made to fit a specific function to the correlation using the Orthogonal distance regression (ODR) package in Python. In order to do this, though, we had to correct for a certain thing: the majority of data lie in the low AOD values region, making the correlation less visible and the graph more difficult to read. Therefore, we first averaged the fluxes for a reference value, chosen to be the average of all fluxes. Subsequently, a new binning system was introduced for the AODs. The set of AOD values taken is shown in Table 1.

Initial Bin	Final Bin
0	0.02
0.02	0.04
0.04	0.06
0.06	0.08
0.08	0.1
0.1	0.15
0.15	0.2
0.2	0.3
0.3	0.4
0.4	0.6
0.6	1.0

Table 1: AOD values where the average flux is taken.

Then, we once more averaged the flux for each set of AOD values and set the standard deviation from each bin as the flux error. Subsequently, a correlation plot was constructed. A more detailed explanation will be provided in section 3.1.

Finally, we examined how the number of observations changed with different AOD values and if there was an AOD value for which there was no correlation.

3.1 0.2 to 1 TeV

Upon closer examination of the light curve in the energy range of 0.2 to 1 TeV, it was discovered that there were some negative and NaN values that lack any physical meaning. Therefore, we investigated the source of these observations. These anomalies originated from observations with low counts. The light curve estimator yielded negative or exceedingly low values when its $\sqrt{\text{TS}}$ was negative or low. Consequently, these problematic values were removed by filtering them out, with the additional condition that the light curve table should comprise only flux values whose $\sqrt{\text{TS}}$ exceeds 3. This choice will be explained in more detail in subsection 3.3.

The subsequent step was to calculate the light curve on a nightly basis. This was done by calculating

CORRELATION NIGHTWISE (complete dataset)

(a) Correlation plot for 0.2 to 1 TeV. On the y-axis, we can find the flux values, and on the x-axis the AOD values. In magenta, we can find the attempted fit. In the pink box, we find the Pearson Correlation value. The flux values are presented with their respective error.

CORRELATION NIGHTWISE LOWER ENERGY

(b) Correlation Plot for 0.2 to 1 TeV with the average flux. On the y-axis, we can find the flux values and on the x-axis the AOD values. In magenta, the attempted fit. On the flux values the x bar shows the different binning employed, while the y error bar was calculated as explained in section 3.1. The Pearson Correlation value is -0.74.

Figure 6: Correlation between AOD and flux values for energies ranging from 0.2 to 1 TeV. The left panel shows individual measurements with errors, while the right panel displays the binned averages. In both cases, you can find in magenta an attempt at fitting the data and the Pearson correlation written.

Histogram of Flux Values

(a) AOD threshold 0.05. In pink we find the flux values that have an AOD greater than 0.05, "bad" AOD values. In contrast, in green we find the flux values with an AOD of less than 0.05, "good" AOD values.

Histogram of Flux Values

(b) AOD threshold 0.07. In pink we find the flux values that have an AOD greater than 0.07, "bad" AOD values. In contrast, in green we find the flux values with an AOD of less than 0.07, "good" AOD values.

Figure 7: Two histograms related to different AOD thresholds. On the left the threshold is 0.05 and on the right is 0.07. Showing the impact on the flux values observed. Energy range: 0.2 - 1 TeV.

the light curve daily from 2004-01-01 12:00:00 up to 2020-01-01 12:00:00. This approach ensured that the data collected at night would not be divided into two distinct sets, but rather that each observation period would be fully represented.

Still the histogram had a tail in the low flux values region, as can be seen in the Appendix A.

In order to combine both flux values and AODs, a dataframe was constructed for the fluxes. The dataframe was indexed by the time of the initial data and the columns were made up from the flux and $flux_{err}$. Subsequently, the time was converted to a date format, thereby limiting the data to the date of observation. Afterwards, the AODs were

reindexed, resulting in a dataset with the dates that corresponded to the fluxes dates.

Finally, a Pearson correlation was computed on the flux values and AODs, in addition to generating the correlation plots, which included the AOD values on the x axis and the flux values in the y axis. In order to fit a function, an ODR was performed utilising an exponential as a test function. This is illustrated in Fig. 6a.

This last plot allowed us to choose a better binning for the low AOD values region. The result is shown in Fig. 6b. As one can see, the outcome is clearer. The x bars are included to illustrate the chosen binning. The final result shows a correlation we could correct for.

(a) Correlation Plot for energies from 0.2 to 1 TeV and AOD values less than 0.05. On the y axis we can find the flux values and on the x axis the AOD values. In magenta we can find the attempted fit. In the pink box the Pearson Correlation value.

(b) Correlation Plot for energies from 0.2 to 1 TeV and AOD values less than 0.07. On the y axis we can find the flux values and on the x axis the AOD values. In magenta we can find the attempted fit. In the pink box the Pearson Correlation value.

Figure 8: Correlation plots between flux values and AOD values, comparing data under different AOD threshold conditions (less than 0.05 vs. less than 0.07). Energy range: 0.2 - 1 TeV.

3.1.1 Different AOD values

We created histograms for different AOD values, shown below in Fig. 7.

As one can observe, the change is evident: there are far more counts with an AOD value greater than 0.05, represented by the pink points in the left panel, than those below this threshold, represented by the green points in our graph. One can also notice that most of the "bad" counts, the flux values with an AOD value greater than 0.05, can be found at the left of the histogram, meaning at lower flux values. This aligns with our hypothesis: the higher AOD values the lower fluxes measured.

On the other hand, in the right panel with a threshold of 0.07, we have far more counts at the "good" AOD values region, but the correlation with flux is stronger, as we will see in the correlation plots in Fig. 8. Another thing to point out is the structure made by the "bad" fluxes that remain in the left part of the histogram.

As expected, the correlation in the case of less than 0.05 AOD is extremely weak, with a p-value of 0.950, indicating that no statistically significant correlation exists between AOD values less than 0.05 and flux values. In contrast, for the case of 0.07, a correlation of -0.21 is observed with a p-value of 0.018. Consequently, it cannot be stated that no correlation exists for AOD values less than 0.07.

However, with 0.07 there is a larger quantity of flux values than in the case of 0.05. Therefore, correcting for the AOD values would be important, to not lose these quantities of data.

3.2 1 to 10 TeV

Following the steps described in the subsection 3.1 with the same fluxes selection to filter out the non physical meaning values. The histogram can be found in the Appendix A.

The histogram show two distinct structures, and, in particular, an excess at lower flux values. This may be attributed to the AOD values affecting our measurements. Nevertheless, further investigation is required. In order to get a better grasp on the matter, an attempt was made to divide the flux values by a specific AOD threshold, as will be seen in the subsection 3.2.1. The correlation plot found in this case can be found in Fig.10a.

As can be observed from Fig.10a, there is a clear correlation between the variables. The next step was to enhance the visibility of the correlation. For this, we calculated the average flux with respect to the AOD values, just like in section 3.1. The result can be seen in Fig. 10b. As one can observe, the correlation becomes more evident. From Fig. 3.1 and Fig. 10b, one might think that the selected function is not ideal for the fitting, however, the primary objective of this analysis was to evaluate the correlation between the AOD and flux values.

3.2.1 Different AOD values

The histograms calculated for the different AOD values can be found in Fig. 11.

As can be observed in the figure, at the value of 0.05, there is a greater number of flux values with an AOD greater than 0.05. However, these flux values are more prominent towards the left side of the spectrum. This shape is also evident in the 0.07

Figure 9: Correlation Plots for Different $\sqrt{\text{TS}}$ thresholds. In blue we find the low energy flux values, while on red the high energy flux values. On the left, we see the correlation plot with a $\sqrt{\text{TS}}$ greater than 1, and on the right the $\sqrt{\text{TS}}$ greater than 3. On the left with a black circle we note the flux value lower than expected. Not seen on the right

(a) Correlation Plot for energies from 1 to 10 TeV. On the y axis we can find the flux values and on the x axis the AOD values. In magenta we can find the attempted fit. Written on the white box on the labels is the fit function used. In the pink box we find the Pearson Correlation value. The flux values are presented with their respective error.

(b) Correlation plot for energies from 1 to 10 TeV with the average flux. On the y axis we can find the flux values and on the x axis the AOD values. In magenta we can find the attempted fit. On the flux values the x error bar is showing the different binning employed, while for the y error bar it was calculated as explained in section 3.1. In the pink box we find the Pearson Correlation value, being -0.75.

Figure 10: Correlation plot between AOD and flux values for energies from 1 to 10 TeV. The left figure shows individual measurements with error bars. While in the right panel we can find the error bars in the vertical axis, while the x bars show the different binning used.

histogram. This results in a more pronounced spike in the right part of the spectrum, which was not as evident in the 0.2 to 1 TeV case.

Correlation results can be seen in Fig. 12. As expected, the findings align with those of the preceding case (0.2 to 1 TeV). Similarly to the earlier results, the Pearson correlation is considerably less significant for AOD values below 0.05. In this case, the p-values for the Pearson correlation of the AOD values of 0.05 and 0.07 are 0.57 and 0.004 with a Pearson correlation of 0.06 and -0.24, respectively. Therefore, the same conclusion can be drawn as in the previous case: it would be beneficial to correct

for the atmosphere.

3.3 $\sqrt{\text{TS}}$ choice

The selection of the value of $\sqrt{\text{TS}}$ greater than 3 was made for two main reasons. The first reason is that we wish to ensure the statistical significance of our analysis. Therefore, according to the definition, a value greater than 3 is significant. The second reason is illustrated in Fig. 9, which shows the low and high energy flux values correlation plots put together. In blue we find the low energy values and in red the high energy values. It can be observed that there is a flux value that is lower than expected, as

(a) AOD threshold 0.05. In pink the flux values that have an AOD greater than 0.05, "bad" AOD values. In contrast, in green we find the flux values with an AOD of less than 0.05, "good" AOD values.

(b) AOD threshold 0.07. In pink the flux values that have an AOD greater than 0.07, "bad" AOD values. In contrast, in green we find the flux values with an AOD of less than 0.07, "good" AOD values.

Figure 11: Two histograms related to different AOD thresholds. On the left the threshold is 0.05 and on the right is 0.07. Showing the impact on the flux values observed. Energy range: 1 - 10TeV.

(a) Correlation Plot for energies from 1 to 10 TeV and AOD values less than 0.05. On the y axis we can find the flux values and on the x axis the AOD values. In magenta the attempted fit. In the pink box we find the Pearson Correlation value.

(b) Correlation Plot for energies 1 to 10 TeV and AOD values than 0.07. On the y axis we can find the flux values and on the x axis the AOD values. In magenta the attempted fit. In the pink box we find the Pearson Correlation value.

Figure 12: Correlation plots between flux values and AOD values, comparing data under different AOD threshold conditions (less than 0.05 vs. less than 0.07). Energy range: 1 - 10 TeV.

indicated by the circled point. Upon examination, its $\sqrt{\text{TS}}$ value was less than 3 (1.29). Therefore, it would be reasonable to eliminate the non-significant values. However, this raises the question of how many values are to be excluded. As the objective of this analysis was to consider all available data, this could have a significant impact. In response to this issue we looked for how many values were being removed. That were for the low energies, only one value, and for the high energies, five observation dates. Therefore the issue of filtering an important amount of data does not arise. Finally, the graphs with $\sqrt{\text{TS}}$ greater than 3 can be found in Fig.9. The low flux value is gone and the Pearson correlation are comparable.

4 VERITAS analysis

The Very Energetic Radiation Imaging Telescope Array System (VERITAS) is a ground-based gamma-ray instrument operating in southern Arizona, USA. It is an array of four 12m optical reflectors designed for gamma-ray astronomy. These imaging Cherenkov telescopes are calibrated to achieve the highest sensitivity from 85 GeV to 30 TeV.

In this study, 2250 unfiltered observations of the Crab Nebula were employed, totaling approximately 721 hours of observations between 2007 and 2024. No specific quality cuts were applied, except for selecting datasets with a statistical significance where the square root of the test statistic ($\sqrt{\text{TS}}$) was at least greater than 3, similarly to what is described in section 3.3. Although we anticipate around 20% systematic uncertainties on the flux, our current focus is primarily on the statistical analysis.

It's critical to note that VERITAS does not observe during the summer, between July and September, due to local monsoon conditions, as highlighted in Fig. 13, which depicts the first three years of operations and AOD values linearly interpolated from the Copernicus datasets for each run. Considering this, the majority of the observations were conducted under very clear sky conditions, which likely minimized the impact of atmospheric aerosols on the measurements (Fig. 14).

As for the H.E.S.S analysis, we performed a spectral fit and examined the flux histograms. Finally, we looked at the correlation plots between the interpolated AOD values per run and flux values, in both 0.2 to 1 TeV energy range and 1 to 10 TeV energy range. A more in-depth look at the AOD variation with different seasonal atmospheric models will be provided respectively in section 4.2 and 4.3.

Figure 13: VERITAS Crab Nebula observation dates and their respective AOD values between 2007 and 2010. In yellow the monsoon season in Arizona is highlighted.

Figure 14: Histogram of AOD values for each VERITAS Crab Nebula observation between 2007 and 2024. No selection on atmospheric conditions is applied (unfiltered data). Normal atmospheric selection on data on Weather A conditions would narrow down our histograms with the same binning choice to AOD values between 0 and 0.175.

4.1 Correlation with AOD values

We analyzed the AOD distribution for each run in our selected energy ranges separately. To determine the average aerosol level for each run, we used linear interpolation on the Copernicus programme dataframe, followed by cubic spline interpolation to minimize conflicts and NaN values. As mentioned previously and as we can see in Fig. 15a and Fig. 15b most observations were conducted under clear sky conditions with AOD values less than 0.1, in both energy ranges. It can be argued that higher-energy showers penetrate deeper and are more influenced by this phenomenon; indeed, the flux histogram appears to have fewer counts in the higher energy range.

Next, we created a run-wise correlation plot between the AOD values and flux points and calculated the Pearson linear correlation coefficient r in each energy range, as shown in Fig. 16. To determine the significance of these correlation coefficients, we checked the p-values for each plot. In the 0.1-1 TeV we observe a $r=0.01$ with a p-value of 0.7 and in the 1-10 TeV energy range $r=0.01$ with a p-value of 0.6, thus we cannot exclude that the weak correlation present is only due to stochastic fluctuations of the flux itself.

It is important to note that our considerations on AOD values do not take into account any atmospheric profile due to altitude. A possible explanation for the lower correlation, compared to the H.E.S.S. findings, is that aerosol might be nearer to the ground in the case of VERITAS.

(a) Histogram of flux values for VERITAS in log space in the energy range 0.1 to 1 TeV. Yellow indicates flux points for AOD values less than 0.1, and green for flux points for AOD greater than 0.1.

(b) Histogram of flux values for VERITAS in log space in the energy range from 1 to 10 TeV. Yellow indicates flux points for AOD values less than 0.1, and green for flux points for AOD greater than 0.1.

Figure 15: Comparison of flux distributions for different AOD thresholds across two distinct energy ranges: (a) low-energy range (0.1-1 TeV), and (b) high-energy range (1-10 TeV). Yellow refers to AOD values less than 0.1, while green is for higher AODs.

Figure 16: Run-wise correlation plots on VERITAS flux points and the AOD values interpolated for the observation time, and the Pearson coefficient r for each energy range. Differently from H.E.S.S. results, no statistically significant correlation appears in these graphs.

4.2 Seasonal atmospheric model

One could argue that even if the maximum aerosol levels are registered during the monsoon season, which is already excluded from VERITAS's observational period, the months preceding or following this event should show significant variation. For this reason, we examined the different AOD distributions between April and June and between September and November. As expected, the new histogram in Fig. 17 shows a shift towards higher AOD values in this time frame, while still indicating overall stationary and good atmospheric conditions. In the typical reconstruction pipeline of the shower images, the IRF assumes a "summer" atmospheric profile model, different from the "winter" model used for other months of observations. This distinction is crucial because season atmospheric con-

ditions and trends, such as temperature, humidity, and aerosol concentration, can significantly impact the Cherenkov light yield and the detector's response. In this section, we aim to investigate whether there is any residual bias that would be visually represented by a clear correlation during the "summer" months.

Figure 17: In red AOD distribution for each run that occurs in the months immediately before (April to June) and after (September to November) the monsoon season in Arizona. For these observations, a 'summer' atmospheric modeling would be used in the normal pipeline for image reconstruction. In blue the AOD distribution for runs occurring when the 'winter' atmospheric model applies.

Between November and April, in the "winter" months highlighted in blue in Fig. 18, we observed low Pearson correlation coefficients in both energy ranges: -0.005 between 0.1 and 1 TeV, and -0.06 between 1 and 10 TeV with a p-value of 0.04. For summer observations, highlighted in red in the same figure, we can see a lack of significant correlation, with a maximum Pearson coefficient of 0.09 between 1 and 10 TeV, and an average p-value of 0.25. Therefore, there is a high likelihood that any observed correlations are due to chance.

Figure 18: Run-wise correlation plots between flux points and their respective interpolated AOD values at observation time. On the left flux points in the energy range between 0.1 and 1 TeV and on the right from 1 to 10 TeV. At the top, we highlight in red runs that occur around monsoon season in Arizona and for which a 'summer' atmospheric modeling would be in the normal pipeline for image reconstruction would be used; at bottom, in blue all other runs for which 'winter' atmospheric model applies.

Figure 19: Run-wise correlation plots between flux points and their respective interpolated AOD values at observation time. On the left flux points in the energy range between 0.1 and 1 TeV and on the right from 1 to 10 TeV. We highlight in blue with a zenith angle higher than 30° , while at the bottom in green, we have runs that had a zenith angle below 30° .

4.3 Zenith angle dependency

As the zenith angle of our telescope increases, the path length that rays from celestial objects must travel through the Earth's atmosphere also increases. Scattering processes and absorption by high-altitude aerosols can lead to a greater reduction in the intensity of the observed light. Consequently, we expect a higher correlation at higher zenith angles.

Given that the Crab Nebula generally has a higher zenith angle at the H.E.S.S. site, we would anticipate that VERITAS should show lower correlation points. However, we still expect some dependency of our correlation values on the observation angle. We divided our observation data into runs with zenith angles lower than 30° and those higher than 30° . Across all energy ranges, the correlation plots (Fig. 19) show Pearson coefficients of the same order of magnitude with no evident variations. The values for zenith angles greater than 30° are somewhat lower, likely because they provide more limited information about our source.

5 Conclusions and summary

The analysis of AOD distribution within the selected energy ranges revealed important insights into the influence of atmospheric aerosols on gamma-ray observations using H.E.S.S. and VERITAS. In the VERITAS datasets (Section 4), no significant correlation was detected between AOD values and gamma-ray observations, suggesting that under clear sky conditions, the influence of aerosols on gamma-ray measurements is minimal. The low Pearson correlation coefficient might also indicate that aerosols could be concentrated nearer to the ground, explaining their reduced impact on gamma-ray observations.

H.E.S.S. observations (Section 3), on the other hand, showed a correlation between AOD values and gamma-ray observations at different energies. Some observations at low AOD values showed weak correlations, indicating that even minimal aerosol presence can affect the measurements, though the impact is less pronounced.

This study emphasizes the necessity of applying atmospheric corrections to the Instrument Response

Functions (IRFs) on the accuracy of air-shower reconstructions. It is necessary to consider seasonal variations in aerosol levels, particularly during the biomass-burning season in Namibia, which can introduce significant variability in atmospheric conditions. This consideration is crucial for enhancing the sensitivity of ground-based telescopes to transient very-high-energy (VHE) emissions from sources like the Crab Nebula.

6 Future prospects

Future work should focus on re-evaluating the systematic uncertainties of our telescopes to improve the robustness of the findings. Incorporating continuous atmospheric monitoring into the analysis pipeline can refine the corrections applied to the observations, providing more accurate results.

Additionally, coordinated observations using multiple telescopes across different time zones can offer more comprehensive coverage and mitigate the effects of aerosols rising in different parts of the world, thereby improving the chances of capturing transient events.

Finally, the development and deployment of new detectors, such as the Cherenkov Telescope Array (CTA), with improved sensitivity and resolution on IRFs, can further enhance the capabilities of ground-based gamma-ray observatories.

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Finally this research used ASTROPY software packages (<https://www.astropy.org>; Astropy Collaboration 2013, 2018, 2022), MATPLOTLIB (<https://matplotlib.org>; Hunter 2007) and PANDAS (<https://pandas.pydata.org/docs/>; Pandas collaboration 2024) software packages.

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A Appendix

In here, we can find the HESS graphs without the new binning; therefore one can see the whole data. In Fig. 20 one can see the different distribution of the fluxes from 0.2 to 1 TeV runwise.

Figure 20: Histogram of flux values in log space from 0.2 to 1 TeV.

In Fig. 21 one can see the different distribution of the fluxes for the 1 to 10 TeV energy range runwise. There are some excesses at low flux values even for this plot, maybe due to the high AOD values.

Figure 21: Histogram of flux values in log space from 1 to 10 TeV.